

Research Article

Comparative Study on Growth Performance of *Clarias gariepinus* Fry Fed on Live Foods and Artificial Diet

Onuoha, P. C., *Elezuo, K. O., and Odubiro, A. T.

Department of Fisheries Technology, Federal College of Fisheries and Marine Technology, Victoria Island, Lagos

Abstract

The growth performance and feed utilization studies were carried out on *Clarias gariepinus* fry using live food and artificially formulated diet for 12 weeks in plastic tanks. The fish were fed with diet A (*Daphnia spp*), B (*Artemia nauplii*) and C (40% Crude protein formulated diet) at 5% of their body weight. Each dietary treatment was replicated twice with 20 fry per replicate. Percentage Weight Gain (PWG), Mean Growth Rate (MGR), Specific Growth Rate (SGR) and Food Conversion Ratio (FCR) were calculated. Data were subjected to One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at $p=0.05$. The highest growth rate was recorded in the group fed on diet C, with an average percentage weight gain of 66.89%, followed by fry fed on diet A, with an average percentage weight gain of 42.10% and the least percentage weight gain was recorded in fry fed on diet B with average percentage weight gain of 40.63%. The best food conversion ratio was in fry fed diet C, with FCR of 2.01, follow by fry fed diet A, with FCR of 3.17 and then those fed on diet B, with FCR of 3.54. The mean growth rate and specific growth rate was highest in fry fed on diet C, with MGR and SGR of 2.1284g and 3.4311%/day respectively, followed by fry fed on diet A with MGR and SGR of 1.6687g and 2.0689%/day respectively. The least MGR and SGR were recorded from fry fed on diet B, with MGR and SGR of 1.6294g and 1.9933%/day respectively. The study revealed that *Daphnia* can be used to replace *Artemia* in the diet of *Clarias gariepinus* fry, provided that effort is being made to ensure all year round culture and rich culture medium that will allow the *Daphnia* to be nutritionally rich and complete for optimal growth and development of catfish fry.

Keywords: Catfish, *Daphnia*, Feed utilization, Growth, Hatchery

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Introduction

Fish culturists have grown rapid interest in the growth rate of *Clarias gariepinus*. This is due to the encouraging information on the biology of the fish. It grows fast, it is omnivorous, it is hardy, can tolerate adverse conditions, such as low dissolved oxygen, high ammonia and it commands good price in the market because of the quality of the flesh (Carreon *et al.*, 1973 and Bardach *et al.*, 1972).

Despite all the advantages associated with the fish, it is difficult to meet the demand of *Clarias* fingerlings from the hatchery, by the prospective fish farmers in Nigeria. This is due to high mortality rate associated with the fry stage, as a result of starvation, space, competition and most importantly poor feed quality and management. Therefore, increasing the fry production will depend on a better techniques for the reproductive biology and better techniques for the rearing of larvae and fry (Colt, 1986). Any kind of confinement for animal results in a lessening of the animals' ability to find the right quantity and quality of food it requires. It follows that keeping any kind of animal in confinement requires providing good quality food for the animal's needs. This means that the feed must contain all the essential amino acids, vitamins, minerals, carbohydrates, fatty acids and glycerol, in right quantities, for their healthy growth.

Feed formulation is essentially applied nutrition for good growth of fish. To formulate practical fish diets, one needs to know the crude protein level, energy level, specific amino acid levels, crude fibre level and ash level (FAO, 1980). According to Robinson (1989), feed stuffs contain protein in amounts ranging from 15-50 percent. This falls within the range of protein requirement for optimum growth of several fish species. Protein requirement for *Clarias* fry is high, about 50% and that of adult is lower. Fish meal is the only major ingredient that singly meets all the nutrient requirement of any stage and type of fish. However, the shortage and high cost of quality fishmeal, impose real constraints in the formulation of optimal diet. Dry feeds (starter diets) for fry and fingerling fish, and post larval shrimp are supplied in powdered form, micro crumbles, crumbles and small pellets. The main problems associated with the manufacture of starter feeds, stem from the need to blend the full range of essential ingredients within a small particle, Goddard (1996). Faeces and unconsumed food also pose real problem because they contribute to the loading of materials that significantly changes the water quality adversely. This is a common problem in formulated feeds.

In the hatchery, fry are more susceptible to deterioration of water quality that results from feeding with formulated diet. Hence, feeding with live food becomes very imperative.

Live food organisms are more important for the growth of fish during culture, especially their early stages of development (fry and fingerlings stages). Such live organisms are largely plankton, insects and worms. Their use in aquaculture is not only known to enhance growth, but also to increase the rate of survival of fish during these critical stages, for they have more protein required for growth, low metabolisable energy which cannot develop into fat, they are easily digestible to fish and they reduce the rate of infection (Jhingran, 1983; Lubzens *et al.*, 1984; Holm, 1987).

Zooplanktons are small aquatic animals like Rotifers, cladocerans, ostracods and copepods, consumed live as first food by many fish fry after yolk absorption to the first 45 days of life (Jhingran and Pullin, 1985). They are therefore critical to the successful operation of any fish hatchery (Bardach, 1978).

Artemia is a type of zooplankton universally used as food for fish fry, *Artemia* nauplii play a very important role in the feeding schedule for the production of fish fry, however, many fish farmers in Nigeria cannot afford it because it is very expensive, and since the target is to produce fish for the teeming population at an affordable price, there is need therefore to source for a cheaper nutritionally comparable and locally available live food organisms like *Daphnia*. *Daphnia* is a cladoceran, phylum: Arthropoda, class: Crustacean, subclass: Branchiopoda, family: Daphnidae, Huet (1986). Huet (1986), further explained that the crustaceans are one of the most important of zoological groups which are food for fish and that the higher crustaceans are consumed by adult fish, while the lower crustaceans are the principal plankton food eaten by fry and young fish. This most common and important of the crustaceans are the cladocerans, small crustaceans from ¼ to 3mm in length, *Daphnia* species are particularly abundant in recently filled small ponds or those manured by organic matter, in small pools of water etc. They are popular among aquaculturist because of their rapid populations growth and their rich nutritional value (Ang, 1973).

The earlier mentioned water quality problem and increasing cost of formulated diets and raw materials are posing great constraints to large scale production of fish fry, therefore, the use of live planktonic organisms is becoming increasingly important in developing countries for increased hatchery production especially of *Clarias* fry.

Though, it is evident that a reasonable and acceptable proportion of scientist are engaged in nutritional research, it is disheartening to note that more of the work are concentrated on adult stage of life cycle, while minimal emphasis has been laid on larval and fry stages, where growth potential is highest (Colt, 1986). There is therefore the need to study the growth performance of *Clarias gariepinus* fry fed live foods and formulated diets.

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of this study are:

- (1) To compare the growth performance of *Clarias gariepinus* fry, fed on live foods and artificial formulated diet.
- (2) To compare the survival rate of *Clarias gariepinus* fry, fed on live foods and artificial formulated diet.

Materials and Methods

Source and Maintenance of Experimental Fish

The fry of *Clarias gariepinus* used for the experiment was gotten from artificial breeding using hypophysation method. The fish was injected with pituitary gland, marcerated in 1ml of 0.9% physiological salt solution in a test tube. The weights of the brood fish used were 0.9kg and 0.85kg of male and female respectively. The eggs were stripped and fertilized with milt gotten by sacrificing the male.

The eggs were incubated in plastic basins, and Kakabans were used in holding the eggs. Maintenance of the fry was done by aerating the water continuously, feeding with live *Daphnia* spp. The wastes and faeces were siphoned out daily. This was done for 3 weeks before the commencement of the experiment.

The experiment lasted for duration of twelve weeks. Sampling of fish was done fortnightly and at the end of the experiment.

Experimental Set-Up

The experiment was conducted in three plastic tanks labeled A, B and C in two replicates to reduce sampling error (total of six tanks). The tanks have the same area of 0.1075m². Prior to stocking, the tanks were properly washed and dried. They were then filled to $\frac{3}{4}$ with fresh tap water that has been dechlorinated. Dechlorination was done by leaving the water outside for 48 hours. 120 fry were randomly selected and 20 fry were stocked in each basin. Air pump of 1500W was used in aerating. The water parameters were checked with the aid of the U-10 Horiba multi-parameter water

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checker. The experiment was well monitored and the level of water was uniformly maintained throughout the duration of the experiment. The water was changed once in two days, food and faecal waste were siphoned daily.

Diet Components and Treatment

The three experimental diets used are:

- DIET A - *Daphnia spp.* = Treatment A
- DIET B - *Artemia nauplii* (Control diet) = Treatment B
- DIET C - Artificial formulated diet = Treatment C

Daphnia Culture and Harvesting

Before the *Daphnia* culture, *Daphnia spp* were gotten from the water in small gutters around Federal College of Fisheries and Marine Technology , Victoria Island , Lagos poultry dung which served as the culture media was collected from a nearby farm. The dung was kept in a tank, in which water was added, it was left to ferment for 3 days. After the third day, the mixture was sieved with a cloth in 3 plastic basins, not allowing any particles (substrate) to pass through. The basins were covered with mosquito nets.

TABLE 1: Composition of experimental diets (percentage by weight)

FEED INGREDIENTS	% COMPOSITION
Dry brewery waste	10.840
Wheat offal	10.840
Fish meal	16.955
Soyabean	16.955
Blood meal	16.955
Cotton seed cake	16.955
Vitamin/mineral premix	1.000
Oyster shell	1.000
Bone meal	1.000
Salt	0.500
Oil	3.000
Starch	4.000
Total	100.000

Few *Daphnia spp* was added to the water (nutrient gotten from the poultry dung) and left for about 7 days. By this time the *Daphnia spp* have multiplied in abundance and ready for use.

The *Daphnia spp* were harvested with a hand net. They were being scooped with the net and rinsed with water, before being used to feed the fry.

Hatching of *Artemia*

The *Artemia* cyst were hatched in a plastic bottle. The cyst were added to a 0.9% saline and constantly aerated for 24 hours. The plastic bottle was turned upside down because container with flat bottom have dead areas in the corners and are not ideal for maximum hatching rate, Schumann (2001), and are placed in a cup to make it stand (balance), the bottom of the bottle being cut out to give it an opening. After, hatching (which was sometimes extended to 36 hours, to allow for maximum hatching), the aerator was disconnected, so as to enable one to harvest the nauplii. Before harvesting, the culture was allowed to settle down for about 5 minutes.

Hatched empty cells floats on the surface unhatched cysts sink to the bottom. Since the newly hatched nauplii are attracted to light, Schumann (2001), a torch light was shined at the middle of the bottle, to concentrate the nauplii at the centre, where they were being siphoned out in to another container. Unused nauplii were kept in the refrigerator.

Composition, Formulation, Processing and Storage of Formulated Diet

The diet was formulated to contain crude protein of 40%. The inclusion levels of the different ingredients are shown in Table 1.

Processing and Storage

Grinding of the feedstuff was done with the aid of a milling machine (Wiley Cutting Mill, Model: U29-B). The milling was done twice to ensure proper grinding. The soybean was put inside a scientific electric cooker and toasted at moderate temperature for one hour until the seed coat became brown, before grinding. Toasting of the soybean was done to destroy the antinutritional factors.

The feed stuffs were mixed manually. The starch was prepared and poured into the feedstuffs and then mixed thoroughly to form a homogenous mixture. The starch act as a binder and also aid feed stability in water.

The homogenous mixture was pelleted with the aid of a meat mincer. The pelleted feeds were sufficiently sundried for three days. The pellets were stored by keeping them in a water proof sack and stored in a dry cool place, protected from moisture and oxidation of fats (Dupree, 1984).

Feeding

The fry were fed 4 times daily, (7am, 11am, 3pm and 7pm). They were fed with ration of 5% of their body weight. The *Daphnia spp* (Diet A) were sieved and rinsed with water before being administered to the fry. The *Artemia nauplii* (Diet B) were separated from the cyst and rinsed properly with fresh water before being fed to fry. The formulated diet (Diet C) was ground to particles that can be taken by the fry and this particle range was gradually increased with time (as they grow). Each diet was administered to the fry in the plastic vessels.

Weighing and Measuring

At the commencement of the experiment, before the feeding trial, the initial weights and lengths of the fry from each replicated tank was gotten. This was done by random sampling of 5 fry from each tank for each of the diet/ treatment replicates. Average weights and lengths were noted from each replicate with the aid of a sensitive balance (Model: EB-3305) and meter rule respectively.

Measurement of Water Quality Parameters

Temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen and conductivity were measured with the aid of the U-10 Horiba water checker. This was done every week throughout the period of the experiment.

Determination of Growth Indices, Survival and Feed Utilization.

Indices of Growth and Survival

Percentage Weight Gain (%)

The percentage weight gain was calculated as follows:

$$\frac{\text{Weight gain (g)} \times 100}{\text{Initial weight (g)}}$$

$$\text{Initial weight (g)}$$

Mean Growth Rate (MGR)

The mean growth rate was expressed as average relative growth and was calculated as follows:

$$\text{MGR (mg/g/day)} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{0.5 (W_2 + W_1) t} \times 100$$

Where W_1 = Initial weight of fish (g)

W_2 = Final weight of fish (g)

t = Experiments period in days

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Specific Growth Rate (SGR)

The special growth rate was calculated by using the formula.

$$SGR = \frac{\ln(W_2) - \ln(W_1)}{T} \times 100$$

Where $\ln(W_2)$ = the natural logarithm of the final weight at time t, and $\ln(W_1)$ is the natural logarithm of the initial weight. It is expressed in %/day Goddard (1996)

Survival

The survival rates were calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Survival (\%)} = \frac{\text{standing biomass}}{\text{Total no of fry stocked}} \times 100 \text{ (Goddard, 1996)}$$

Mortality

The mortality rate was calculated using the formula:

Mortality rate (%) = Total no. of fry stocked - no. of fry recovered at the end of the experiment / Total no. of fry stocked x 100

Indices of Food Utilization

Food Conversion Ratio (FCR)

The FCR was calculated using the formula:

$$FCR = \frac{\text{Food consumed (g)}}{\text{Weight gain (g)}}$$

Protein Efficiency Ratio (Per)

The protein efficiency ratio was calculated using the formula:

$$PER = \frac{\text{Weight gain in (g)}}{\text{Crude protein fed (g)}}$$

Where crude protein fed is total feed fed x % crude protein in diet. Given the weight of food consumed.

Statistical analysis

Data resulting from the experiment were subjected to one- way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. The determination of significant mean differences among individual means was done at P = 0.05 using Fisher's least significant difference (LSD).

Results

Growth Performance and Feed Utilization Parameters

The growth performance of *Clarias gariepinus* fry fed on diet A, B and C is presented in Table 2. The fry fed on diet C gave the highest final mean weight of 1.571g at the end of the experiment, followed by the fry fed on diet A with final mean weight of 0.705g and the least was shown in fry fed on diet B with the final mean weight of 0.667g.

TABLE 2: Data showing the growth parameters and feed utilization of fry of *Clarias gariepinus* fed on live food and formulated diet for 12 weeks (MEAN± SEM).

Parameter	DIET A (<i>Daphnia spp</i>)	DIET B (<i>Artemia nauplii</i>)	DIET C (Formulated Diet)
Duration of experiment (days)	84	84	84
Number of Fry Stocked	20	20	20
Number of survival at end of experiment.	18	17	10
Survival rate (%)	90	85	50
Mortality rate (%)	10	15	50
Average Initial weight (g)	0.124	0.125	0.088
Average final weight (g)	0.705	0.667	1.571
Average weight increase (g)	0.096	0.090	0.923
Average initial length (cm)	2.43	2.50	2.47
Average final length (cm)	5.16	4.98	8.10
Average weight of food supplied (g)	0.3897	0.3719	0.4092
Percentage weight gain (%)	42.10±0.10 ^a	40.63±0.10 ^a	66.89±0.20 ^b
Mean growth rate	1.6687±0.05 ^a	1.6294±0.05 ^a	2.1284±0.04 ^b
Specific growth rate	2.0689±0.05 ^a	1.9933±0.06 ^a	2.3563±0.05 ^b
Food conversion ratio	3.17±0.08 ^b	3.54±0.06 ^b	2.01±0.05 ^a
Protein efficiency ratio	0.58±0.03 ^a	0.55±0.03 ^a	1.29±0.04 ^b

Mean values in each row with similar superscripts are not significantly different ($p>0.05$).

The highest percentage weight gain was shown in fry fed on diet C, with a percentage weight gain of 66.89%, followed by fry fed in diet A, with percentage weight gain of 42.10% and the least was shown in fry fed on diet B, with a percentage weight gain of 40.63%.

The mean weight and length increase was highest in fry fed on diet C, with a mean weight increase of 0.248g, and mean length increase of 0.92cm. This was followed by fry fed on diet A with mean weight and length increase of 0.096g and 0.45cm respectively. The least mean weight and length increase was obtained in the fry fed of diet B, with mean weight and length increase of 0.090g and 0.41cm respectively.

The mean growth rate of fry fed on diet C was highest, with mean Growth rate 2.1284g followed by fry fed on diet A with mean growth rate 1.6687g and the lowest was in fry fed on diet B with mean growth rate of 1.6294g.

TABLE 3: Data showing weekly water quality records

Week	DO (mg/l)			pH			Temperature (°C)			Conductivity (µS/cm)		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
1	8.50	8.50	8.50	8.0	8.0	8.0	26.5	26.5	26.5	0.058	0.058	0.058
2	8.51	8.53	7.58	8.0	8.1	8.1	26.0	26.0	26.0	0.070	0.080	0.080
3	8.45	8.30	7.49	8.2	8.0	8.3	26.0	26.0	27.0	0.070	0.100	0.075
4	8.50	8.48	7.59	8.3	8.5	8.0	27.0	26.0	27.0	0.067	0.100	0.070
5	8.45	8.45	7.50	8.0	8.5	8.5	26.0	26.0	26.0	0.075	0.090	0.067
6	8.48	8.44	7.59	7.9	8.3	8.8	26.0	27.0	26.0	0.100	0.080	0.080
7	8.59	8.60	7.68	8.0	8.3	8.9	26.0	26.0	26.0	0.825	0.078	0.078
8	8.60	8.60	7.80	7.8	8.3	8.1	26.0	26.0	26.0	0.068	0.059	0.080
9	8.51	8.52	7.90	8.0	8.3	8.0	26.5	26.5	26.5	0.080	0.058	0.080
10	8.60	8.59	7.56	8.1	8.4	8.0	26.5	26.5	26.5	0.070	0.090	0.078
11	8.58	8.59	7.69	8.3	8.2	8.2	26.0	26.0	26.0	0.066	0.080	0.078
12	8.61	8.65	7.72	8.2	8.8	8.8	26.0	26.0	26.0	0.070	0.100	0.080

Legend: A, B and C represents Diet A, Diet B and Diet C treatments respectively.

The specific growth rate, (SGR) was highest in fry fed on diet C with SGR of 2.3563g, followed by fry fed on diet A, with SGR of 2.0689g, and the least specific rate was shown in fry fed on diet B, with SGR of 1.9933g.

The condition factor for fry fed on diet. B was highest with condition factor of 0.5400, followed by fry fed on diet A, with a condition factor of 0.5131 and the least was shown in fry fed on C, with condition factor of 0.2954. The fry fed with diet C has the highest

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percentage mortality rate of 50% while those fed with diet A have the lowest mortality rate of 10%.

The feed utilization parameters of fry fed on diet A, B and C are shown in Table 2.

The best food conversion ratio was shown in fry fed on diet C, with FCR of 2.01 followed by fry fed on diet A, with FCR of 3.17 and the worst FCR was shown in fry fed on diet B with FCR of 3.54.

The fry fed on diet C have the highest protein efficiency ratio (PER) with PER of 1.29 followed by fry fed on diet A, with PER of 0.58 and the lowest protein efficiency ratio was obtained in fry fed on diet B, with PER of 0.55.

Water Quality Records

Table 3 shows the water quality records for 12 weeks. The mean values of dissolved oxygen level for *Clarias gariepinus* fry on diets A, B and C were 8.53, 8.52 and 7.72 mg/l respectively. The mean of pH level for *Clarias gariepinus* fry fed on diet A, B and C were 8.06, 8.28 and 8.31 respectively, these values fall within the acceptable range of pH for fish fry production.

The mean values of temperature level for *Clarias gariepinus* fry fed on diets A, B and C were 26.17°C, 26.21°C and 26.29°C respectively. These values fall within the acceptable range of temperature for fish fry production.

The mean values of conductivity level for *Clarias gariepinus* fry fed on diets A, B and C were 0.07µS/cm, 0.08µS/cm and 0.08µS/cm respectively. These values fall within the range of conductivity level for fish fry production.

Discussion

Discussion

The mortality rate was highest in fry fed on diet C, with 50% mortality; this however may be due to the fact that not all the fry responded well to the formulated diet. According to Lannan *et al.*, (1986), a wide variety of feeds have been tried by Dabrowski *et al.* 1978; Khan and Mukopadyay, 1973, but, all have resulted in either increased mortality (due to poor acceptability by fry) or decreased growth (due to nutritionally incomplete diets), when compared to live plankton. Observation on the high survival of fry fed on diet A and B agrees with those reported previously that live organism reduces mortality thereby increasing survival rates of early stages of fish (Alikunhi,

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1957; Browley *et al.*, 1978; Jhingran, 1983; and Duray and Bagarino, 1984; Drouin *et al.*, 1986).

The water quality parameters monitored were all within the acceptable range recommended for fresh culture (Omoregie *et al.*, 1991). The difference in growth and survival rates of the fry reported in this study can therefore not be attributed to poor water quality.

The highest growth performance was observed in fry fed on diet C, followed by fry fed on diet A and the least growth performance was observed in fry fed on diet B, though, previous observations by Jhingran (1983) Lubzen *et al.* (1984), Drouin *et al.* 1986 and Holm (1981) have shown live organism enhance the growth of fish, at their early stages of development. Also other projects by Reitan *et al.* (1994), Yoshimatsu and Kitajima (1996) and Aguigwu (1999), confirmed that fry fed on live food organism (plankton) have better growth performance whereas, the result of this study is not so. This however, may be due to various factors ranging from biological to environmental factors. But as shown in the result, environmental factors (water parameters) were within the acceptable range; therefore it is not the cause. According to Yoshimatsu and Kitajima (1996), Quantity of Zooplankton fed is important for maximum growth. They studied daily feeding ration of *Artemia* (20, 40, 60 and 80% larvae body weight), the highest growth was shown in Larvae fed on *Artemia* at 80% of their body weight once daily and that fed on 60% of their body weight four times daily, from this result it was concluded that feeding rate should be about 60% of their body weight and feeding frequency should be more than twice a day to prevent inefficient utilization of *Artemia*, however in this study 5% of fry body weight was fed to fry also the feeding frequency was fluctuating during the period of *Daphnia spp* low production, which might have been the cause of deviation from the observations mentioned above.

However, Colt (1986), stated that, in the early stages of fish's life when larval growth is rapid, it is vital not only that the proper quantity and size of zooplankton be given, but that the zooplankton, contain the appropriate nutrients. Problems have been encountered over the nutritional quality of rotifer (*Branchionus plicatilis*) in Japan, where it is used as the live food for fish larvae and these were related to the food organisms used for its culture (Cho *et al.*, 1985). Also, Clare (2001) stated that zooplankton are "what they eat", this means that their nutritional quality depends on what they feed on (i.e. what is used for their culture). For the purpose of this study, poultry dung was used to culture *Daphnia*, *Daphnia spp* were also gotten from small gutter, and their nutritional value not known, hence, the *Daphnia spp* used may not be nutritionally rich

enough to supply the fry, all the nutrients needed for rapid growth, which may account for the deviation from various literature by Jhingran (1983), Lubzens *et al.* (1984) and all others, also, during the culture, production of *Daphnia*, depletes, which may be due to water pollution, hindering the feeding frequency. According to Clare (2001), *Daphnia* has been proven to be very sensitive to halide concentration, like chlorine and fluoride in tap water, which are extremely toxic to *Daphnia*, they are sensitive to metal ion like sodium, potassium etc, all these may be responsible for the depletion in the *Daphnia* culture, since tap water was used for the culture and the halide and metal ion concentration not known. And subsequent this affects the feeding frequency of the fry. Also, water temperature affects the life span of *Daphnia* (Clare, 2001). High temperature results in a short life span and vice -versa.

The fatty acid composition of *Artemia* nauplii may vary in a manner similar to that of *Brachionus* and *Daphnia* depending upon the source of the *Artemia* eggs, the organism upon which they are reared or location (Cho *et al.*, 1985).

The feed utilization was highest in the fry fed on diet C, this also may be as a result of the reasons stated above, since it was observed by Shim and Bajral (1982), Watanabe *et al.* (1983) and Aguigwu (1999) reported that feed utilization is high when fry are fed with live food. Also, Cho *et al.* (1985), stated that values of Protein Efficiency Ratio (PER) and NPU of living foods (*Branchiounus*, *Artemia*, *Tigriopu*, *Moina*, *Daphnia*), measured with Carp and Rainbow trout were high and it is clear that all of these organisms are valuable protein sources (Cho. *et al.*, 1985).

However, the condition factor was highest in fry fed on diet B (*Artemia*), followed by fry fed on diet A and the least was observed from fry fed on diet C. this shows that, though, fry in basin A and B growth was not in accordance with previous literature, they are in a very good state of health.

Conclusion

From the results obtained from this study, it can be inferred that in feeding with live food, one should ensure that adequate quantity is provided and the quantity provided contain the required amount of nutrient for rapid growth.

In conclusion, live food organisms should be used to feed fry at early stages, which later can be supplemented with formulated diet. *Daphnia* can be used to replace *Artemia* in

the hatchery, provided that effort is being made to ensure all year round culture and rich culture medium that will allow the *Daphnia* to be nutritionally rich and complete.

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